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Report on Annual Meeting 2026**

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Table of Content

Executive Summary	2
1. Introduction	3
2. 17 March 2026: 1 st RIANA Users Meeting.....	4
3. 18 March 2026: 1 st RIANA Users Meeting & 2 nd RIANA Annual Meeting.....	5
4. 19 March 2026: 2 nd RIANA Annual Meeting	7
5. Programmes of the 1 st RIANA Users Meeting & 2 nd RIANA Annual Meeting	8

Executive Summary

This deliverable gives an overview of the 2nd RIANA Annual Meeting that took place 17 – 19 March 2026 in Heraklion/Crete, Greece, and was hosted by the leader of work package 5. The highly successful meeting combined strategic discussions, technical exchanges, and networking activities, thereby supporting the effective implementation of the Horizon Europe project RIANA.

Scheduling the RIANA Annual Meeting back-to-back with the 1st RIANA Users Meeting ensured diligent use of resources and enabled effective exchange between RIANA Users and Research Infrastructures both during a joint session and informal discussions during breaks and a poster session.

Within the three days of the RIANA Annual Meeting, RIANA bodies including the General Assembly, Executive Board, Junior Scientist Board, and Nano Strategy Board profited from satellite meetings that were held in hybrid mode as the entire RIANA Annual Meeting.

Overall, the 2nd RIANA Annual Meeting 2026 met its objectives. It provided a comprehensive review of the second project year and allowed to align on the work plan midterm of the project. This meeting strengthened the collaboration and team spirit across the consortium and set the course for concentrated outreach and dissemination actions in view of the adapted access rules that are subject of the 1st amendment to the Grant Agreement.

1. Introduction

Key figures

The RIANA Annual Meeting 2026 was held as a hybrid meeting from 17 to 19 March 2026 in Heraklion, Crete, Greece, hosted by the Foundation for Research and Technology – Hellas (FORTH). The meeting brought together RIANA consortium members (see Fig. 1) to review project progress, discuss strategic priorities, coordinate future activities, and strengthen collaboration across all work packages (WPs). The consortium reviewed the implementation of the second project year and aligned on the work plan for the remainder of the project.

Of the 83 participants of the RIANA Annual Meeting, 54 joined in person and 29 connected remotely via Zoom.

Highlights

A major highlight of the meeting was the 1st RIANA Users Meeting, scheduled back-to-back with the 2nd RIANA Annual Meeting at the same venue. By organizing both meetings and aligning the agendas, the RIANA project partners were able to directly discuss with users who are RIANA's most important stakeholders, thus enabling a valuable exchange about user needs, access procedures, scientific services, and cooperation opportunities in RIANA projects.

The Annual Meeting demonstrated the extraordinary engagement of the consortium and confirmed the continued progress of RIANA towards its strategic objectives.

Figure 1: Participants of the 1st RIANA Users Meeting and 2nd RIANA Annual Meeting 2026.

2. 17 March 2026: 1st RIANA Users Meeting

The first day was all about the 1st RIANA Users Meeting that represented an important milestone in strengthening the connection between RIANA and its user community. The wide distribution of the origin of the Users beyond Europe was particularly impressive. It demonstrates that the knowledge transfer between European Research Infrastructures (RIs) to Users that are not familiar with the Ris and may not have access to Ris through other means is effective and satisfies a demand.

The meeting enabled direct interaction between users, stakeholders, and the RIANA project partners. Discussions focused on available services, user expectations, scientific opportunities, and practical access to RIANA infrastructures.

In parallel, governance meetings were held: the RIANA Executive Board and the RIANA Junior Scientists Board – the ensemble of the Smart Science Cluster – met in preparation of the Annual Meeting.

The day concluded with a poster session and a get-together, where technical discussions initiated during the Users Meeting were continued in an informal networking environment, supporting community building and stakeholder engagement.

Figure 2: Mustafa Shalaby, a RIANA User from Egypt, emphasized the important role of RIANA enabling effective knowledge transfer from Europe to Africa in the joint session of the 1st RIANA Users Meeting and the 2nd RIANA Annual Meeting. Credit: Michael Stuckelberger.

3. 18 March 2026: 1st RIANA Users Meeting & 2nd RIANA Annual Meeting

Joint session

A joint session closed the 1st RIANA Users Meeting and kicked off the 2nd RIANA Annual Meeting. Around 100 participants on-site and around 50 connected remotely listened to the welcome speeches of the host, namely the Chairman of the Board of Directors of FORTH, Vassilis Charmandaris, and the Acting Director of FORTH's Institute of Electronic Structure and Laser, Emmanuel Stratakis. These presentations were followed by an introductory talk by the project coordinator Michael Stuckelberger (DESY). The main part of the morning session consisted of pitch talks covering the techniques offered by all 8 RIANA networks:

- e-DREAM
- RADIATE
- LEAPS
- LENS
- EUROnanoLAB
- EUSMI
- HPC
- Laserlab

In these focused presentations, the Junior Scientists representing the RIANA Smart Science Cluster introduced the techniques available within the RIANA project. The subsequent discussions with RIANA users proved very fruitful for both sides – the Users and the members of the RIANA consortium – in view of future collaborations.

The first session was followed by a group picture of the participants of both meetings.

Site visit

After the group picture, all participants visited different laboratories of FORTH. The visit gave the partners a good impression of the research conducted at the host institution and of the techniques available – the delay caused by the numerous questions of the participants speaks for itself. The visit prompted further discussions throughout the rest of the meeting and beyond, which demonstrates how engaging such on-site tours are with a lasting impact on the interaction between Users and Research Infrastructures. After the site visit, the official programme of the 1st RIANA Users Meeting ended.

Parallel sessions

The afternoon session began with parallel working group meetings, which focused on both individual work packages (WPs) and cross-work-package topics. The cross-work-package meetings were particularly effective as they allowed for the discussion of numerous details and the development of future strategies in close collaboration between the work packages. Given the success of this format, more time will be allocated for targeted cross-work-package meetings at future annual meetings. In parallel, closed sessions of the RIANA Nano Strategy Board and the Project Review Panel took place.

Inter-project connection: FHERITALE

The coordinator of the EU project FHERITALE, Antonio Rosato (University of Florence), presented the aims and the current developments of the FHERITALE project and highlighted points of connection with the RIANA project. Michael Stuckelberger took the opportunity to thank Antonio Rosato for the reciprocal invitation to present RIANA at a FHERITALE meeting 2025.

Innovation Contest

The innovative potential in the RIANA consortium was evidenced by the presentations of the two winners of the 1st RIANA Innovation Contest: Simona Bianco (MAX IV) presented her project on “Designing hybrid nanomaterials for stimuli-responsive soft actuators,” and Jakub Jagielski (AMU) presented his project on “Bioactive lipid cuboplexes: a novel synergistic strategy for resensitizing antibiotic-resistant bacteria.” Congratulations to the two winners and best wishes for their innovative projects!

Working dinner

In the evening, a working dinner provided another opportunity to continue scientific, technical, and organisational discussions within and between work packages. The coordinator delivered a speech that emphasised the importance of collaboration, mutual support, and shared objectives, and thanked the RIANA partners for their work over the past year. To stimulate new conversations during the dinner, playful and interactive activities were organized, and seating was assigned at random, giving participants the chance to exchange ideas with colleagues they would not normally sit with.

Figure 3: Plenary presentation by the project coordinator Michael Stuckelberger (DESY). Credit: Tom Minniberger.

4. 19 March 2026: 2nd RIANA Annual Meeting

The second day started with the General Assembly (GA). This meeting was open to all beneficiaries – however, only GA members with voting rights were allowed to vote. During the GA meeting, a vote was held on the membership of a new RIANA beneficiary. The University of Twente had applied to become a new RIANA beneficiary in order to provide 300 Transnational Access (TNA) hours. Prior to the final vote by the GA, the RIANA Executive Board (EB), and the RIANA Nano Strategy Board (NSB) reviewed the application and recommended the membership of the University of Twente as regular RIANA beneficiary. After discussion, the GA voted unanimously to approve the application that will be considered in a future amendment to the Grant Agreement.

Following the General Assembly, Anna Santoro, the European Commission’s project officer responsible for RIANA, presented the latest developments in the INFRA work programme and the future FP10 framework programme, including activities related to transnational access.

The work packages were then presented in plenary, with an overview of current results and upcoming developments for each followed by a lively and active discussion among the RIANAers – the identification of many participants with RIANA became obvious when Lakshmi Bhaskaran, responsible for Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI), probed the mood in the room through a game.

A further highlight was the interactive call to participants to

- a) submit suggestions for additional reviewers for RIANA proposals, given the increased reviewing workload, and
- b) write down concrete small activities for the RIANA project that each participant will implement in the following week.

The Annual Meeting concluded with a brainstorming session with the title “How to attract more scientific and SME users?”. The same question had led throughout the two meeting days, and the brainstorming session collected a number of concrete approaches to expand RIANA’s scientific and SME user base in the years ahead.

Overall, the 2nd RIANA Annual Meeting was a great success. It allowed the consortium to review the second project year, align on the work plan in highly productive meetings, and agree on a set of concrete activities to expand RIANA’s user base. Finally, all participants left the meeting full of energy and motivated to contribute toward RIANA’s success, and with smiles on their faces.

5. Programmes of the 1st RIANA Users Meeting & 2nd RIANA Annual Meeting

Tuesday, March 17, 2026

The entire day was allocated to the 1st RIANA Users Meeting and the related programme is highlighted in light blue. For details of the programme – most importantly, a list of all contributions by existing and prospective RIANA users – we refer to Fig. 4 in the public RIANA deliverable D5.1.¹

Regular dark blue font describes closed sessions of RIANA boards in preparation of the Annual Meeting.

Time	Activity
08:30	Registration
09:00	1 st RIANA Users Meeting See detailed agenda here: Program Users Meeting
10:40	Coffee break
11:20	Continuation of 1 st RIANA Users Meeting See detailed agenda here: Program Users Meeting
13:00	Lunch
14:00 – 15:00	RIANA Executive Board (EB) Meeting - Closed session for EB members <i>Room: Stelios Orfanoudakis</i>
14:20	Continuation of 1 st RIANA Users Meeting See detailed agenda here: Program Users Meeting
15:30 – 16:30	RIANA Smart Science Cluster (SSC) Meeting - Closed session for JSB members <i>Room: Stelios Orfanoudakis</i>
15:40	Coffee break
16:00	Continuation of 1 st RIANA Users Meeting See detailed agenda here: Program Users Meeting
18:00	Poster Session and get-together

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/19645612>

Wednesday, March 18, 2026

Time	Activity
08:30	Registration
09:00	<p>Joint session of RIANA Users Meeting and Annual Meeting</p> <p>Welcome words</p> <p>Vassilis Charmandaris, Chairman of the Board of Directors of FORTH</p> <p>Emmanuel Stratakis, Acting Director of Institute of Electronic Structure and Laser of FORTH</p> <p>Michael Stuckelberger, Project coordinator, DESY</p> <p>Pitch talks: Available techniques in RIANA networks</p> <p>e-dream: Nicolas Gauquelin, UAntwerp</p> <p>Radiate: Masedi Masekane, RBI</p> <p>LEAPS: Laura Paradis Fortin, ALBA</p> <p>LENS: Debasish Saha, FZJ-JCNS</p> <p>EUROnanoLAB: Andrius Žutautas, UKaunas</p> <p>EUSMI: Jakub Jagielski, AMU</p> <p>HPC: Yannic Kitten, FZJ-JSC</p> <p>Laserlab: N.N.</p>
10:45	Group photo
11:00	Visit to FORTH laboratories
13:30	Lunch
14:30	<p>Parallel WP meetings: session 1</p> <p>WP2 + WP4: room: Costas Fotakis</p> <p>WP3: room: Alkiviadis Pagiatakis</p> <p>WP5: room: Stelios Orfanoudakis</p> <p>WP6: room: Γ 100</p>

Time	Activity
15:15	Parallel WP meetings: session 2 WP2 + WP6: room: Costas Fotakis WP3 + WP5: room: Alkiviadis Pagiatakis WP4: room: Stelios Orfanoudakis
16:00	Coffee break
16:30	Parallel WP meetings: session 3 WP2 + WP5: room: Costas Fotakis WP3: room: Alkiviadis Pagiatakis WP4 + WP6: room: Stelios Orfanoudakis NSB: room: Γ 100 PRP: digital per Zoom
17:30	FHERITALE project presentation Antonio Rosato, University of Florence
17:45	Presentation of Junior Scientist Innovation Contest Designing hybrid nanomaterials for stimuli-responsive soft actuators Simona Bianco, MAX IV Bioactive Lipid Cuboplexes: A Novel Synergistic Strategy for Resensitizing Antibiotic-Resistant Bacteria Jakub Jagielski, AMU
18:15	End of 1st day meeting
20:00	Working dinner

Thursday, March 19, 2026

Time	Activity
09:00	GA Meeting <i>Open to all project partners</i>
10:00	Introductory statement Anna Santoro , Policy Officer, European Research Executive Agency (REA) (remote talk)
10:15	User access User access Marketa Sjögren, WP3 Leader (MAXIV) Proposal Review Panel Karol Adam Janulewicz, PRP chair User travel reimbursement Daniela Stozno, WP3 co-Leader (Laserlab AISBL) Talk by coordinator Michael Stuckelberger, Project Coordinator (DESY)
11:30	Coffee break
12:00	Customised access to scientific service Coordination of the scientific service and operate the RIANA helpdesk Regina Ciancio, WP2 Leader (AREA) Rafal Dunin-Borkowski, WP2 co-Leader (FZJ) Scientific Service N.N., JSB chair
12:45	Lunch break
14:30	SME access SME access Giancarlo Panaccione, WP4 Leader (CNR) Platform of Industrial Contact Officers (PICO) Noor Navaz, PICO chair (ESRF)
15:15	Outreach, dissemination, and impact RIANA Outreach activities Gaston Garcia, WP6 Leader (UAM)
15:30	Training and education RIANA Training activities Panagiotis Loukakos, WP5 Leader (FORTH)

16:00	RIANA Project Management Management status of the project Michael Stuckelberger, Project Coordinator (DESY) Tom Minniberger, Project Manager (DESY)
16:15	RIANA DEI Officers Status report of the DEI officers Inka Manek-Hönninger (CNRS) & Lakshmi Bhaskaran (HZDR)
16:30	Coffee break
17:00	Brainstorming How to attract more scientific and SME users?
18:00	Q&A, AOB, farewell
18:15	End of 2nd day meeting